

Reduction of Cobalt Borate by Hydrogen

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Reduction of the crystalline cobalt borate, $\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$, by hydrogen proceeds according to
$$\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{H}_2 = \text{Co} + 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}.$$

The reduction is slow up to 550° , but becomes increasingly rapid with increase of temperature. At 750° reduction is more than 90%, but complete reduction is hindered by fusion of the borate itself. The reduction process, like those for copper and nickel borates, is accompanied by activated adsorption.

The present investigation is a continuation of our previous work in this laboratory on copper and nickel borates (this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 555; *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, **21**, 81). No information is available in the literature on the reducibility of cobalt borate by carbon or hydrogen. Results on the reduction of a cobalt borate is reported in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt Borate

Preparation of cobalt borate by metathesis from aqueous solution was more difficult than the corresponding copper or nickel salt. The light pink precipitate first formed easily changed colour to blue simply on exposure to air, indicating decomposition to basic compounds. Fusion methods were also not entirely satisfactory because of the difficulty of purification and isolation of a borate having a definite composition.

A very interesting but simple method was developed for the preparation of a pure cobalt borate. The starting material was a dihexammino-dicobaltic borate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{B}_4\text{O}_7)_3 \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$, prepared according to the method of Khundkar and Haider (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1956, **284**, 312). On slowly heating this compound at 450° , the deep yellow crystals decomposed, giving off both ammonia and water vapour, and finally a violet-blue cobalt borate was obtained. This on analysis conformed to the composition $\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$. (Found: B, 22.8, 22.5; Co, 20.2, 21.0. Calc. for $\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$: B, 22.9; Co, 20.8%).

Procedure

The apparatus was the same as that employed for reduction of copper borate (*loc. cit.*). The cobalt borate (previously heated to remove any moisture, and cooled) was taken in a platinum boat and placed in the reaction temperature zone in a closed system, which had earlier been evacuated and filled with pure hydrogen at atmospheric pressure. The progress of the reaction was followed by noting the decrease in gas volume at different intervals of time; these volumes were corrected for N.T.P. and plotted against time in Fig. 1. The water vapour formed during the reaction was absorbed in P_2O_5 , placed in a small boat at the exit (cooler) end of the reaction tube.

Analysis of the Products of Reduction.—The solid products of reduction were free B_2O_3 , metallic cobalt, and cobalt borate. The amount of free B_2O_3 gave the extent of reduction. ~~Cons.~~

care was necessary to extract this from unreduced cobalt borate, and it was possible only with anhydrous methanol. Hot water or even hot methanol decomposes cobalt borate (giving methyl borate in the latter case).

DISCUSSION

For the different experiments carried out at temperatures between 500° and 750°, equal amounts of cobalt borate (0.4 g.) were taken so that the results could be directly compared. Progressive consumption of gas with time (Fig. 1) shows that the reaction is somewhat slow up to 550°, taking nearly 160 to 180 minutes to reach equilibrium. At temperatures between 600° and 750°, the major reaction takes place during the first hour.

FIG. 1

The theoretical amount of hydrogen required for complete reduction to cobalt (without affecting B_2O_3) is 31.9 c.c. At 600° and above, the total volume of hydrogen consumed is higher than this. It had earlier been noted that B_2O_3 was not reduced at all by hydrogen at these temperatures. It is therefore obvious that the reduction process is associated with adsorption of gas, presumably on the reduced metal.

Extent of Reduction at Different Temperatures

Free B_2O_3 was always found in the products of reduction; this could be extracted, without affecting the residual cobalt borate, by cold anhydrous methanol. The mechanism of reduction of cobalt borate appears to follow the general course, as found earlier with copper and nickel borates, viz.,

The amount of free boric anhydride (as extracted by careful and repeated extraction with anhydrous methanol) was determined in the product of each experiment and expressed in terms of percentage of total B_2O_3 (present in $CoO.3B_2O_3$).

TABLE I
Products of reduction of cobalt borate by hydrogen at diff. temp.

$\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ taken = 0.400 g., corresponding to 0.294 g. B_2O_3 .

Reduction.		B_2O_3 in methanol extract.		B_2O_3 in unchanged borate.		Mean value of reduction.
Temp.	Period.					
500°	195 min.	0.096 g.	32.6 %	0.192 g.	65.4 %	33.6 %
550°	145	0.148	50.3	0.139	47.4	51.4
600°	130	0.198	67.4	0.094	32.0	67.7
650°	110	0.222	75.5	0.067	22.8	76.4
700°	90	0.245	83.2	0.050	17.1	83.1
750°	90	0.266	90.4	0.028	9.6	90.4

The data in Table I (column 4) could be taken to represent the extent of reduction at the relevant temperature. But this was further corroborated by the determination of total B_2O_3 in the unchanged borate (*i.e.*, residue from anhydrous methanol extract), and expressed as percentage (Table I, column 6). The difference between 100 and these values would also represent the extent of reduction; the mean of the two values was actually taken in the last column.

Instead of continuing for the same period of time, the experiments were continued till the system came to equilibrium, *i.e.*, when the rate of consumption of hydrogen came down to < 1.0 c.c. per hour.

The extent of reduction is small at 500°; this increases with temperature and reaches only 90% at about 750°. A plot of the percentage of reduction against temperature (not shown here) indicates that the slope of the curve between 500° and 600° is greater than that between 600° and 750°. This is explained by the observation that the cobalt borate tends to sinter above 600° and actually fuses between 700° and 750°. This means that complete reduction of cobalt borate by hydrogen is not practically feasible. The reduction, however, proceeded to over 90%.

In an attempt to stop fusion of cobalt borate, two experiments were carried out at 700° and 750° respectively with MgO as incorporate. In presence of MgO, the rate of reaction was very much accelerated (Fig. 1), but the total gas consumption was more or less the same. Whether the reduction went to completion could not be confirmed on account of the meagre amount of free B_2O_3 found in methanol extract. This is possible only if MgO reacts (partially or completely) with cobalt borate as follows:

This can also explain the rapidity of reduction in presence of MgO; CoO is known (*cf.* Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic & Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. 14, p. 563) to be very rapidly reduced by hydrogen at 700°.

Phenomenon of Adsorption

In Table II is presented a set of data showing (i) the volume of hydrogen (N.T.P.) consumed during reaction, as obtained from curves in Fig. 1, (ii) the volume of hydrogen required for reduction at different temperatures, as calculated from the extent of reduction, and (iii) the difference of the above two, representing the volume of hydrogen adsorbed.

TABLE II

[$\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ taken in each experiment = 0.400 g.]

Temp.	Reduction Mean value.	Actual vol. (total) of H_2 consumed.	Volume of H_2 reqd. for reduction.	Volume of H_2 in excess.
500°	33.6 %	15.1 c.c.	10.7 c.c.	+4.4 c.c.
550°	51.4	25.3	16.4	8.9
600°	67.7	35.9	21.6	14.3
650°	76.4	37.7	24.4	13.3
700°	83.1	39.3	26.5	12.8
750°	90.4	40.5	28.9	11.6
700° (with 0.1 g. MgO) ..		38.7	..	..
750° (with 0.1 g. MgO) ..		41.2	..	..

The data in Table II leave no doubt that the system $\text{CoO} \cdot 3\text{B}_2\text{O}_3\text{—H}_2$ also falls in general line with the other systems (viz., involving $\text{CuO} \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ and $2\text{NiO} \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$) so far studied in that this reduction process is also accompanied by adsorption. In all probability the adsorption takes place on the finely divided metal after it has been formed by reduction of the borate. It should be noted that the adsorption is relatively low up to 550°, after which it increases, but the values between 600° and 750° do not differ much. A common factor in all the three systems, mentioned above, is that this adsorption has a positive temperature coefficient (activated adsorption) as noted by Taylor *et al.* for certain oxides (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2168).

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